

D2.1. Catalogue of services

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Definition

Short name	Definition
AgroServ RI	AgroServ is a consortium of research infrastructures that enables research community to use facilities, resources and services to conduct research in the field of sustainable and resilient agriculture, agroecological transition and One-Health approach (Figure 1)
Resource	Any physical or digital asset or infrastructure made available to Users. Resources are generally tangible (concrete) elements and most of the time do not require an instantiation. Resources include instruments, equipment, data(sets), software, biological samples, etc. (Figure 1)
Service	The mean or a process a user employs to deliver results. Services are usually intangible although they may also include tangible elements, since it relies on a set of resources. Services require instantiation by a Service Provider. Services include experimentations, observations, analysis, modelling, compute, data and material storage, training, consultancy, etc. (Figure 1)
Installation	Usually a physical facility (often part of an organisation (Legal entity)) where experiments are performed (analysis, observations, experimentations, etc). It generally includes different resources and provides several services of the same type. It can be also considered as the elementary units for which cost calculation can be defined (Figure 1)
Experiment	A planned activity carried out by partners of a project, who are USERS, i.e. a group of persons who uses one or more facilities (Figure 1)
Access/Service/Resource Provider	Member (-s) of an organisation (Legal entity) to that manages and delivers Services and Resources of the installation to Users (Figure 1)
Research Infrastructure	An organisation that enables the research community to use specific facilities, resources, and services to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields
National infrastructure	An organised group of local infrastructures with governance recognised by national authorities (Figure 1)
Local infrastructure	A group of facilities located in one site depending on one institution (or more) (Figure 1)
RI/Access Managers	A RI/Access Manager are members of an organisation that coordinates the access to research infrastructures services. Their responsibilities include managing and supporting researchers during the pre-proposal phase for TNA serving as a liaison between research staff and project stakeholders (Figure 1)
Catalogue	The customer-facing list and description of all current installations, Services and Resources that can be offered by AgroServ RI to users. It is a subset of the Portfolio.
Portfolio	An internal list that details all the Services and Resources offered by a Service/Resource Provider, including those in preparation, live and discontinued.
User	The individual that primarily benefits from and uses Services/Resources (Figure 1)
AgroServ Central Hub	A central organisation providing several common functionalities between installations such as project submission form, form for populating information about services, installations ecc. In this Hub, all the projects are collected.

Figure 1 Main catalogue of services definition and their functional relationships

Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
ARIA	Access to Research Infrastructure Administration
CatRIS	Catalogue of Research Infrastructure Services
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategic Framework for Research Infrastructure
GDPR	General data protection regulation
ISIA	Information System for Infrastructure Administration
MERIL	Mapping of the European Research Infrastructure Landscape
OWL	Web Ontology Language
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RI	Research Infrastructure
TNA	Transnational Access
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
WP	Work Package

PROJECT SUMMARY

AgroServ in a Nutshell

Ensuring a viable agroecological transition towards sustainable and resilient agri-food systems

Agricultural land depletion, the loss of biodiversity and the growing scarcity of natural resources are some of the complex challenges we face in this century. Whether due to the competition for land-use or due to the tensions on agricultural modes of production, the necessity to adapt our current agricultural production methods to continue producing agricultural goods while concomitantly maintaining, preserving, and adapting the ecosystems, is a necessity.

AgroServ was thus born from the need for a collective action capable of enhancing the sustainability of food systems and food chains, while safeguarding human, animal, and environmental health, and preserving natural resources and biodiversity and mitigating climate change. The project was launched with the objective to better align (scientific) approaches and capabilities, and more effectively and efficiently use resources to ensure a viable agroecological transition towards sustainable and resilient agri-food systems.

By bringing together several types of expertise, disciplines, and technologies, and by integrating the competence and know-how of ecologists, agronomists, biologists, chemists, bioengineers, analysts, social scientists, and economists, AgroServ is designed to advance our knowledge on agronomic and husbandry practices. While there is a focus on the threats and risks on agroecosystems, it simultaneously supports the development of new agroecological practices by fostering transdisciplinarity and integrating a socio-economic dimension in the offer to researchers.

1 Summary of deliverable

The overarching mission of AgroServ is to support research and innovation by providing customised and integrated Research Infrastructure services in view of achieving a sustainable and resilient agriculture and supporting agroecological transitions by:

- providing access to innovative, customised and efficient services (physical, remote and virtual);
- enabling interdisciplinary research by developing higher levels of integration of multi-RI services.

Work Package 2 aims to establish a common service/resource catalogue framework for describing and offering RI services/resources in a user-friendly searchable format, in particular to design and implement catalogues and software tools to operationalise the integration and customisation of services available to the users across different disciplines and all AgroServ RIs (Task 2.1).

Figure 2 The RIs at the core of AgroServ

Task 2.1 aims to provide users with an online catalogue of customised services available within AgroServ by describing the installations, their service/resources available to carry out Transnational Access projects and making them findable and accessible by researchers, research groups, communities, projects, organisations, innovators and businesses, funders and policy makers.

This task works towards a common service/resource definition model and service/resource management for RIs to reach a harmonised approach to service/resource catalogues. Catalogue is a key service of AgroServ and this report describes the work undertaken in Task 2.1 and the current

development status of cataloguing (D2.1). AgroServ catalogue is expected to facilitate structuration and improve quality of services offered both within single RIs and multiple RIs levels. It promotes efficient and multi-inter-transdisciplinary research offering new opportunities to users, new tools to RI managers and new communication strategies for RI communities.

A working group evaluated the technologies, methodologies and experiences acquired by CatRIS, EOSC and ARIA. A service/service provider description model compatible and interoperable with existing service catalogues was provided, including:

- A tool for collecting and updating metadata with a controlled vocabulary on the general description of RIs, their service offerings, resources and availability as close as possible to the installation managers;
- A catalogue of research installations available online and accessible to all user profiles to discover and use the full potential of European agroecological research.

The collection and centralisation of information describing the installations, their service offer, their resources, and their availability will be used to feed the process of optimising scientific projects by providing all the elements necessary for their scientific and technical evaluation.

Standard models for describing providers and services already exist and their application in the AgroServ catalogue ensure compatibility and interoperability with the main existing catalogues such as the EOSC marketplace. The APIs provided by these catalogues allow automatic information updates without requiring installation and service managers to connect to them. It is then important to control the vocabulary used to annotate it and provide it in machine-readable formats that can be used to feed Deep Learning.

D2.1 outputs contributes :

- to define the whole procedure of project evaluation and optimisation from the deposit portal to the fulfilment of access conditions, including TNA. The catalogues extend the discovery capabilities of future users and give greater visibility to the entire service offering of AgroServ networks. Therefore, they are the entry point for project developers to submit their applications to the network and start the evaluation and optimisation process. The catalogues will provide links to the network's project submission form (WP1).
- to harmonise the data management rules within the network. Therefore, the development of the catalogues will consider the common requirements in terms of data management and in particular those of the GDPR (WP3).
- to integrate with EOSC marketplace catalogue and CatRIs as well as to be displayed and accessible through AgroServ communication tools, especially on the agroserv.eu website (WP9).

2 Tasks implementation

The AgroServ catalogue requires the following functions:

- Collect information about providers and their services in a single distributed tool.
- Facilitate the use of standard description models compatible with the main existing catalogues.
- Control the vocabulary used to improve data discovery, interoperability and reuse.
- Automate the updating of data in the different catalogues.
- Display information on a web page accessible to all, keeping a level of information adapted to all user profiles.
- Facilitate the discovery of suppliers and services in a catalogue accessible online to the general public.
- Facilitate the discovery of suppliers and services in a catalogue offering filters on the different description data.
- Guide users to AgroServ communication tools and project submission portal.

2.1 Enrichment of standard description models

AgroServ brings together 12 RIs with the common ambition to create a holistic, coherent, interdisciplinary and interoperable cluster of RIs for a sustainable and resilient agriculture and supporting agroecological transitions across Europe. AgroServ gathers all domains (Biological & Medical science, Chemistry & Material science, Information science & Technology, Social sciences) to work together, to capitalise on the progress made in various disciplines and strengthen interoperability amongst RIs and domains. The AgroServ catalogues provide a possibility to integrate multidisciplinary and collaboration across RIs as a first step for heading towards interdisciplinary research. AgroServ catalogues will improve the use and access to RIs for multidisciplinary research by scientists and stimulate innovation by promoting competitiveness and setting the ground for addressing societal challenges and sustainable development goals. Although a culture for interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary collaboration across RIs must develop over time of project implementation, the AgroServ catalogues is key for coordinating the research activities in a multidisciplinary context and to connect and combine the expertise and state-of-the art in each of the disciplines involved.

2.2 Development of the catalogues

2.2.1 Data collection

Task 2.1 has designed and developed a catalogue which provides view and entry point for hierarchical discovery of the 12 AgroServ RIs organised in 145 installations and distributed in 24 European countries (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Number of AgroServ installations per country and Research Infrastructures on which they depend (represented via a colour code). The figure presents the information provided in WP11-20 tables of the Grant Agreement.

To ensure the collection of all information concerning the installations and their services, we have developed a distributed tool accessible to each installation manager, called ISIA for Information System for Infrastructure Administration. Before going any further in description of its functionalities, we need to briefly explain the main principles of this tool. It will allow to better understand how we will use its functionalities to put them at the service of the AgroServ network not only in the framework of WP2 but also of WP1.

ISIA is a web-based application that can be accessed online through any internet browser. It provides an interface for users to manage their resources and projects. Each installation has its own application with a dedicated configuration adapted to their activity. All the installations are then connected in the same network where they benefit from common functionalities such as a project submission form, a special platform called Central Hub to receive all the projects submitted to the network and evaluate them, and forms for entering information about the installations and services. It should be noted that the same service provider may be part of several networks for which the functionalities may have different configurations (no Central Hub, different evaluation process, different models for describing installations and services, etc.).

Figure 4 ISIA – A distributed architecture

My dashboard Organize my work

Summary | Project Tasks | Personal task | My Notes | My Activity

Personal tasks |
 Resources events |
 Projects tasks |
 Tickets events

March 2023

Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat	Sun
27	28	1	2	3	4	5
6	7	8	9	10	11	12
13	14	15	16	17	18	19
20	21	22	23	24	25	26

PROJECT TASKS

No task to do today.

You have no task to finish within three days.

TICKETS

You have no tickets to process.

RESOURCES

You have no events for today.

You have no events for this month.

New events in your resources created in the last three days: 0

Tickets

No ticket

Project Tasks

No task

Figure 5 ISIA - AgroServ Central Hub application interface

List of networks

Add condition to filter results

Show 10 entries Search:

Name	Code	Central Hub platform	Platforms	Network users manager	Network project submissions	Actions
AgroServ	agroserv	AgroServ Central Hub	CEREEP-Ecotron Ile de France, U3E, Lautaret, Ecotron Montpellier, Terrestrial Metatron, IRM Métatron, eDNA, FOREST - Puéchabon, EcogenO, Aquatic Metatron, FOREST - Nouragues, FOREST - O3HP, Ecotron IDF - Ecolabs, Ecotron IDF - Analytical platform, Microcosms, Mesocosms, Macrocosms, SETE - Moulis, 10004-Brandbjerg, 10009-Cultivation Domes / Bily Kriz, 10013-DTU-Ris Experimental fields, 10015-ETRS, 10018-Experimental station Domaninek, 10022-FO3X, ANAEE EUROPE, 10024-BIOBASE, 10025-CENTS, 10026-CROPSYS, 10028-Grassland drought experimental site Bily Kriz, 10032-Hyvtialä-SMEAR II, 10033-Lakkasuo-Siikaneva Peatland experiment, 10042-Kevo Subarctic Research Institute, 10046-Lammi Biological Station, 10050-LIRA, AgriLeach, 10063-Oulanka research station, 10066-PLEN Agro Ecosystems, 10088-Vestskoven, 10089-SMEAR-Agri, Nordic Experimental Peat Agroecosystem (NorPeat), 10097 - Bozhurishte Open Air Platform, 100xx-Douro Living Lab, 20001-ALGOLAB, 20002-Antwerp Meso-scale Ecotron, 20008-Ecotron Hasselt University, 20013-Ecotron TERRA Ulige, 20016-Fytoscopes - Growth chamber facility, Brno, Antwerp FATI, 20021-Kainuu fisheries research station, 20028-PLEN Phytotron, 20029-Ecotron DTU, 20030-Silkeborg lake experimental, 20039-Mesodrome, 10090-Experimental station Domaninek - Crop Growth Model, 10098-Tsalapitsa, 40003-Flying Laboratory of Imaging Systems (FLIS), 40004-Brno-Laboratory of metabolomics and isotope analyses, AgroServ, AgroServ Central Hub	Florent MASSOL, David Ponsard, Nicolas Massaia	AgroServ - Pre-proposal submission	
AnaEE ERIC	anaee_europe	Seism	Lautaret, Terrestrial Metatron, eDNA, FOREST - Puéchabon, EcogenO, Aquatic Metatron, FOREST - O3HP, Planaqua, Ecotron IDF - Ecolabs, Ecotron IDF - Analytical platform, Microcosms, Mesocosms, Macrocosms, Seism, 10004-Brandbjerg, 10009-Cultivation Domes / Bily Kriz, 10013-DTU-Ris Experimental fields, 10015-ETRS, 10018-Experimental station Domaninek, 10022-FO3X, 10024-BIOBASE, 10025-CENTS, 10026-CROPSYS, 10028-Grassland drought experimental site Bily Kriz, 10032-Hyvtialä-SMEAR II, 10033-Lakkasuo-Siikaneva Peatland experiment, 10042-Kevo Subarctic Research Institute, 10046-Lammi Biological Station, 10050-LIRA, AgriLeach, 10063-Oulanka research station, 10066-PLEN Agro Ecosystems, 10088-Vestskoven, 10089-SMEAR-Agri, Nordic Experimental Peat Agroecosystem (NorPeat), 10097 - Bozhurishte Open Air Platform, 100xx-Douro Living Lab, 20001-ALGOLAB, 20002-Antwerp Meso-scale Ecotron, Joensuu root laboratory, 20008-Ecotron Hasselt University, 20013-Ecotron TERRA Ulige, Boreal Forest Regeneration platform (BoFoReg), 20016-Fytoscopes - Growth	Florent MASSOL, David Ponsard, Nicolas Massaia, Katrine Vendelboe		

Figure 6 ISIA - Definition of installations networks

Service providers will therefore have an interface dedicated to their own installations to which only invited users will have access. They also will be able to update information about installations and services via dedicated forms:

Figure 7 ISIA - Access to installation information

The screenshot shows the ISIA dashboard interface. At the top, there is a green navigation bar with icons for Dashboard, Projects, Resources, Tickets, Tools, Config, and a user profile for Florent MASSOL. Below the navigation bar, the main content area is titled 'Ecotron IDF - Ecolabs' with a 'See platform overview' button. A 'Default Description' section is visible, followed by a 'Network 'AgroServ'' section. Underneath, there are two tabs: 'EOSC Provider Data Model Description' (selected) and 'Other Information for the Descriptive Sheet'. A list of installation description forms is displayed, each with a plus sign to expand it:

- Basic Information (Basic form)
- Marketing Information (Basic form)
- Marketing Information Multimedia (List form)
- Classification Information (Basic form)
- Location Information (Basic form)
- Contact Information - Main contact/Provider Manager (Basic form)
- Contact Information - Public Contact (Basic form)

Figure 8 ISIA - AgroServ network installation description forms

The screenshot shows the 'Basic Information (Basic form)' entry form. It contains several fields with descriptive labels and help icons:

- Id**: EPP.BAI.0 - A persistent identifier, a unique reference to the Provider. (Text input field)
- Abbreviation ***: EPP.BAI.1 - An abbreviation of the Provider Name as assigned by the Provider. (Text input field)
- Name ***: EPP.BAI.2 - Full Name of the Provider/Organisation offering the resource and acting as main contact point. (Text input field)
- Website ***: EPP.BAI.3 - Website with information about the Provider. (Text input field)
- Legal Entity ***: EPP.BAI.4 - A Y/N question to define whether the Provider is a Legal Entity or not. (Dropdown menu with 'Yes' selected)
- Legal Status**: EPP.BAI.5 - Legal status of the Provider. The legal status is usually noted in the registration act/statutes. For independent legal entities (1) - legal status of the Provider. For embedded providers (2) - legal status of the hosting legal entity. It is also possible to select Not a legal entity. (Dropdown menu)
- Hosting Legal Entity**: EPP.BAI.6 - Name of the organisation/institution legally hosting (housing) the provider/research infrastructure or its coordinating centre. A distinction is made between: (1) research infrastructures that are self-standing and have a defined and distinct legal entity, (2) research infrastructures that are embedded into another institution which is a legal entity (such as a university, a research organisation, etc.). If (1) - name of the research infrastructure, If (2) - name of the hosting organisation. (Dropdown menu)

At the bottom left, there is an 'Update' button with a checkmark icon. At the bottom right, there is a 'Go to the top' button with an upward arrow icon.

Figure 9 ISIA - Installation information entry form

These forms are the single-entry point for entering installation and service information and will allow automatic dissemination to the various catalogues: AgroServ, EOSC, CatRIs and any other catalogue with an API to automatically update the data.

This single-entry point will avoid Service providers from having to register in each catalogue and enter the same information. The information will be updated automatically and periodically according to the needs of the network.

2.2.2 Catalogues and Descriptives sheets of providers and services

When displayed in the main catalogues, the information displayed in these catalogues will correspond to what has been entered by the installation manager in the EOSC description template forms. For the AgroServ catalogues, we have decided to display additional information that we feel is essential for future users to be able to identify as precisely as possible which installation or service is the most suitable for their project. For example, it seems essential for a user to know the hosting capacities of the installation such as an experimental field site or the daily analysis capacities for a chemical analysis. The catalogues take the form of a rather "classic" homepage to avoid losing users who already have reference points in the main catalogues. The user will find a list of maps corresponding to each installation and service and filters to refine the search.

Figure 10 ISIA - Installation Catalogue homepage v1

On the map, user will find links to:

- the installation's description sheet,
- the installation's services in the service catalogue,
- the installation's website,
- the online project submission form.

By clicking on the description sheet, the user will have access to all the information useful for TNA projects.

40004-Brno-Laboratory of metabolomics and isotope analyses

Parent Infrastructure	
Platform reception	Yes
Active Type	Open
Capacity	1000

Location
Address: 602 00 Brno 60300 Brno

About platform
The metabolomics laboratory provides services of targeted and untargeted metabolome analysis in various biological matrices. Metabolome analysis are performed using tandem analytical techniques: GC/MS and LC/MS/MS with a hybrid LTU (Orbitrap XL mass spectrometer with high resolution and accurate molecular weight measurement. From the targeted analysis, the laboratory is providing the determination of organic acids, amino acids, volatile compounds, phenolic compounds and other primary and secondary metabolites (over 200). The laboratory of isotope analysis provides services of measurements of relative abundance of stable isotopes (¹³C/¹²C, ¹⁵N/¹⁴N, ²H/¹H, ¹⁸O/¹⁶O) in soil-glass-atmosphere continuum. The analysis is performed using an isotope ratio mass spectrometer (IRMSM100) coupled with elemental analysis and allows analyses of solid and liquid samples or with cryogenic pre-concentration in gas samples.

Ecosystem studied
• Other

Climate zone
• Other

Contact us
Name: Sandrine
Mail: sandrine@brno.cas.cz

Figure 11 ISIA - Installation description page v1

The home page of the catalogues as well as the descriptive sheets will evolve over time.

Figure 12 ISIA - Mock-up Homepage Catalogue of installation v2

Figure 13 ISIA - Mock-up installation description page v2

The AgroServ installation catalogue is available at the following address:

<https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/platform/list/agroserv>

2.3 Scientific and technical interoperability

2.3.1 Assistance with controlled vocabulary input

A controlled vocabulary derived from thesauri is essential to ensure interoperability between tools, disciplines and users. It does not only guarantee an unambiguous understanding of the content expressed, but it also allows an identifier (URI) to be associated with it, enabling machines to use it. This is the reason why we are going to provide installation managers with an input aid that proposes terms from thesauri. They will be able to use them to ensure that the information they enter on their installation and services can be reused by humans and machines. Each term entered will have an associated URI. The use of ontology-based tools will then be facilitated and will make it possible to link these terms in machine-readable RDF-type formats. These formats increase the discovery capabilities of search engines and consequently the visibility of the information that uses them.

2.3.2 Automatic connection with other catalogues

By using the EOSC supplier and service description model, we ensure interoperability between our catalogue and the other catalogues that were or will be developed using this model. CatRIs, an AgroServ partner, has already set up a REST API to synchronise data from the EOSC catalogue and populate the same catalogue with information from new suppliers and services. We will therefore take advantage of the experience acquired in synchronising the data collected in the ISIA application to create REST APIs dedicated to each catalogue in which AgroServ services must appear to gain visibility.

The implementation of these synchronizations is scheduled during the 2nd semester of 2023 and a specific documentation will be provided to detail the methods and commands that will be used. Of course, the other catalogues will be able to use the APIs developed to harvest the data we collect and to authorise an ever-greater openness to discovery by machines.

For this last point, we will use the experience acquired by CatRIs to provide data in RDF format and a dedicated API, based on the model provided by EOSC and using OWL ontology terms. These RDF graphs will be enriched by the URIs collected during the proposal of terms from controlled vocabularies as described in the previous paragraph.

These RDF descriptions will not only contribute and encourage discovery, interoperability and interdisciplinarity, but also allow a more efficient reuse of the data we produce.

2.4 Integration with other AgroServ Work Packages

We can identify several actors-users of catalogues. Indeed, research teams and evaluation managers will consult the catalogue to find the most suitable service, while installation managers will have to update information about their services and their installation.

Figure 14 ISIA - Operating diagram WP1 - WP2

We are actively working with the WP1 working group to make the user's journey as smooth as possible, in particular the interactions the users will have with the evaluators during the first phase and the interactions they will have with the service providers in the second phase. The catalogues are central to link the service offers of each installation and the construction, in the Central Hub, of multi-RI projects favouring the emergence of multidisciplinary and innovative projects. Review stages involving the installation managers make it possible to validate the feasibility of the projects in terms of both technical aspects and the necessary resources and availability.

3 Service/Resource Provider Description Template

Figure 15 Building blocks of the Service/Resource Provider Description Template for AgroServ RIs and Installations that provide services (adapted from CatRIs).

3.1 Basic Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
ID	A persistent identifier, a unique reference to the Provider	String (max 30)	One	Mandatory	Yes	No	Delivered by EOSC Catalog
Abbreviation	An abbreviation of the Provider Name as assigned by the Provider	String (max 30)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	AnaEE - Central Hub
Name	Full Name of the Provider/Organisation offering the resource and acting as the main contact point.	String (max 100)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Analysis and Experimentations on Ecosystems
Website	The website with information about the Provider.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://www.anaee.eu/
Legal Entity	A Y/N question to define whether the Provider is a Legal Entity or not.	Boolean	One	Mandatory	Yes	No	Yes

Legal Status	The legal status of the Provider. The legal status is usually noted in the registration act/statutes. For independent legal entities (1) - legal status of the Provider. For embedded providers (2) - legal status of the hosting legal entity. It is also possible to select Not a legal entity.	List of controlled values	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)
Hosting Legal Entity	Name of the organisation/institution legally hosting (housing) the provider/research infrastructure or its coordinating centre. A distinction is made between: (1) research infrastructures that are self-standing and have a defined and distinct legal entity, (2) research infrastructures that are embedded into another institution which is a legal entity (such as a university, a research organisation, etc.). If (1) - name of the research infrastructure, If (2) - name of the hosting organisation.	String (max 100)	One	Mandatory	Yes	No	Research infrastructures that is self-standing and have a defined and distinct legal entity

3.2 Marketing Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Description	A high-level description of the Provider in fairly non-technical terms, with the vision, mission, objectives, background, experience.	String (max 1000)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	AnaEE (Analysis and Experimentation on Ecosystems) will pave the way for understanding the complex impact of today's multiple, interacting global change drivers on terrestrial and aquatic continental ecosystems across Europe. It will forge evidence-based adaptation and mitigation strategies that assure plant, soil, water, biodiversity and ecosystem health today and in the future. Characteristic of AnaEE, its versatile facilities that can simulate environmental drivers from land-use change, pollution, biological invasions, rising atmospheric greenhouse gases concentrations, and increasing extreme events such as droughts and heatwaves. AnaEE will link its facilities with an array of user communities, including scientists, land managers, the bio-economy industry and policy makers, to minimise human environmental impact and maximise societal benefits in a dynamic

							world. Specificity of AnaEE is to integrate, in a single, distributed RI, experimental methods, modelling and experimentation.
Logo	Link to the logo/visual identity of the Provider.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://i.postimg.cc/FHcsQ5WY/logo-anaee-web.png
Multimedia	Link to video, slideshow, photos, screenshots with details of the Provider.	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://www.anaee.eu/
Multimedia Name	Short description of the Multimedia content	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	AnaEE Website

3.3 Classification Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Scientific Domain	A named group of providers that offer access to the same type of resource or capabilities.	List of controlled values (see Table 1)	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes		Agricultural Sciences, Natural Sciences, Social Sciences
Scientific Sub-domain	A named group of providers that offer access to the same type of resource or capabilities, within the defined domain.	List of controlled values (see Table 1)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Agricultural Biotechnology, Agriculture, Forestry & Fisheries, Animal & Dairy Sciences, Other Agricultural Sciences, Veterinary

							Sciences, Earth & Related Environmental Sciences, Environmental Engineering, Biological Sciences, Chemical Sciences
Tags	Keywords associated with the Provider to simplify search by relevant keywords.	String (max 20)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Analysis, Experimentation, Ecosystem, terrestrial, aquatic, ...
Structure Type	Defines the Provider structure type (single-sited, distributed, mobile, virtual, etc.)	List of controlled values (See Table 2)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Distributed, physical, virtual, mobile

3.4 Location Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Street Name and Number	Street and Number of in-incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 50)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Campus CNRS 1 avenue de la terrasse
Postal Code	Postal code of in-incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile	String (max 20)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	91190

	providers.						
City	City of incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 20)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Gif-sur-Yvette
Region	Region of in-incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	String (max 50)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Ile de France
Country	Country of in-incorporation or Physical location of the Provider or its coordinating centre in the case of distributed, virtual, and mobile providers.	List of controlled values (See Table 3)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	France

3.5 Contact Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Main contact/Provider Manager -First Name	First Name of the Provider's main contact person/Provider Manager.	String (max 20)	One	Mandatory	No	No	Michel
Main contact/Provider Manager -Last Name	Last Name of the Provider's main contact person/Provider Manager.	String (max 20)	One	Optional	No	No	Boer

Main contact/Provider Manager -Email	Email of the Provider's main contact person/Provider manager.	Email	One	Mandatory	No	No	michel.boer@anaee.eu
Main contact/Provider Manager -Phone	Phone of the Provider's main contact person/Provider manager.	String (max 20)	One	Optional	No	No	+33(0)677020295
Main contact/Provider Manager -Position	Position of the Provider's main contact person/Provider manager.	String (max 50)	One	Optional	No	No	Director General
Public contact-First Name	First Name of the Provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Michel
Public contact-Last Name	Last Name of the Provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Boer
Public contact-Email	Email of the Provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal or general email to contact Provider.	Email	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	michel.boer@anaee.eu
Public contact-Phone	Phone of the provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal or general phone to contact the Provider.	String (max 20)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	+33(0)677020295
Public contact-Position	Position of the Provider's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 50)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Director General

3.6 Maturity Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Life Cycle Status	Current status of the Provider/Research infrastructure life-cycle.	List of controlled values	One	Optional	Yes	No	Operation
Certifications	List of certifications obtained for the Provider (including the certification body and any certificate number).	String (max 250)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	AGROSE RV : HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01, ENVRI FAIR, EHRIITC

3.7 Dependencies Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Participating Countries	Providers/Research Infrastructures that are funded by several countries should list here all supporting countries (including the Coordinating country).	List of controlled values(See Table 3)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Italy
Affiliations	Providers that are members or affiliated or associated with other organisations should list those organisations here	String (max 30)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	https://www.anaee.eu/about/national-nodes

Networks	Providers that are members of networks should list those networks here.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	AgroServ, ENVRI,
Catalogue	The Catalogue this Provider is originally registered at.	Catalogue ID	1	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/platform/list/agroserv

3.8 Other Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
ESFRI Domain	ESFRI domain classification.	List of controlled values (See Table 4)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Environment
ESFRI Type	If the research infrastructure is (part of) an ESFRI project indicate how the RI participates: a) is a node of an ESFRI project, b) is an ESFRI project, c) is an ESFRI landmark, d) is not an ESFRI project or landmark.	List of controlled values (See Table 5)	One	Optional	Yes	No	Landmark
MERIL Scientific Domain	MERIL scientific domain classification	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Earth & Environmental Sciences
MERIL Scientific Subdomain	MERIL scientific subdomain classification	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Agronomy, Forestry, Plant Breeding Centres, Analytical Facilities, In Situ Earth Observatories, Conceptual Models

Areas of Activity	Basic research, Applied research or Technological development	List of controlled values (See Table 6)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Applied Research, Basic Research, Technological Development, Other
Societal Grand Challenges	Provider's participation in the grand societal challenges as defined by the European Commission	List of controlled values (See Table 7)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Environment, Europe in a changing world, Natural Resources
Sustainable Development Goals	Provider's contribute to the sustainable development goals as defined by European Commission	List of controlled values (See Table 9)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Zero hunger, Clean water and sanitation, Sustainable cities and communities, Responsible consumption and production, Climate action, Life below water, Life on land
National Roadmaps	Provider's participation in a national roadmap.	String (max 80)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c6647f05-874e-4cdd-af70-22ade4759930/language-en

4 Additional service/resource provider information

Figure 16 Building blocks of the Provider Description Template for AgroServ RI (adapted from CatRis) with Additional information.

4.1 Basic and Marketing Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Main image for the descriptive sheet	This image will appear at the top of the description sheet and will be representative of the installation.	String (max 30)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://i.postimg.cc/BbT9V4Q3/le-chateau-de-button-a-gif-sur-yvette-le-31-juillet-2015-1.jpg
Submission project link	Link to your network's project submission form with the selected installation.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://isia.cnrs.fr/ppa/agroserv/agroservpreproposal
Affiliation laboratory	Name of your affiliate laboratory	String (max 100)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://www.anaee.eu/about/national-nodes
Research institution	Name of your Research institution	String (max 100)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://www.anaee.eu/about/national-nodes
Installation capacity	Number and designation of available experimental units	String (max 100)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	0

Accommodation capacity	Number of accommodations available	String (max 100)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	0
Electricity	Power supply available on the installation	Boolean	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Yes
Wifi	Wifi available on the installation	Boolean	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Yes
Highspeed Wifi	High-speed Wi-Fi available on the installation	Boolean	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Yes
Shower	Shower available on the installation	Boolean	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	No

4.2 Keywords

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Keywords	Keywords about your installation	String (max 1000)	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Analysis, Experimentation, Ecosystems, terrestrial, aquatic, ...

4.3 Location and country

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Latitude	Latitude coordinate of the installation (in decimals: 60.924530 for 6055'8.3"N)	String (7)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	48.704754
Longitude	Longitude coordinate of the installation (in decimals: 11.451259 for 1127'04.5"E)	String (7)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	2.135254
Country Code	Country name abbreviation (France: FR)	Controlled values	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	FR

4.4 Experimental installation

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Experimental Installation Type	Enclosed, Open air or Observation	Controlled values	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Open air
Climate Zones	Climates that can be found on the installation	Controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Mediterranean
Ecosystems	Ecosystems that can be found on the installation	Controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Grassland
Environmental Controlled Factors	Environmental parameters measured on the installation	Controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	atmospheric temperature, humidity, soil water content, soil temperature, ...
Environmental Manipulated Factors	Environmental parameters that can be manipulated on the installation	Controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	precipitation, nutrients, ...

Replication Capacity	Number of experimental units available	String (max 100)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	16
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4.5 Analytical installations

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Analytical Installation Type	Stable or Mobile	Controlled values	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Mobile
Categories	Analysis categories that can be found on the installation	Controlled values	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Isotopes
Analysed Parameters	Parameters that can be analysed on the installation	Controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	¹³ CO ₂
Instrument Used	Instruments used to analyse this parameter on the installation	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Picarro G2401
Precision and Sensitivity	Instrument precision and sensitivity	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	10 to 50 ppb
Analytical Capacity	Number of analysis you can realise (ex : 1000 per day)	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Max sampling frequency : 5s 4 analyzers

5 Service/Resource Description Template

Figure 17 Building blocks of the Service/Resource Description Template for AgroServ RI (adapted from CatRis)

5.1 Basic Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
ID	A persistent identifier, a unique reference to the Service/Resource in the context of the EOSC Portal.	String (max 30)	One	Mandatory	Yes		Delivered by EOSC Catalog
Abbreviation	An abbreviation of the Service/Resource Name as assigned by the Provider	String (Max 20)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	AE - VRE
Name	Service/Resource Full Name as assigned by the Provider.	String (max 80)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Agroecology Virtual Research Environment
Service/Resource Organisation	The name (or abbreviation) of the organisation that manages or delivers the service/resource, or that coordinates resource delivery in a federated scenario.	Provider ID	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	LifeWatch ERIC
Service/Resource Providers	The name(s) (or abbreviation(s)) of Provider(s) that manage or deliver the Service/Resource in federated scenarios.	Provider IDs	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	LifeWatch ERIC

Webpage	Webpage with information about the Service/Resource usually hosted and maintained by the Provider.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://www.lifewatch.eu
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5.2 Marketing Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Description	A high-level description in fairly non-technical terms of a) what the Service/Resource does, the functionality it provides and Service/Resources it enables to access, b) the benefit to a user/customer delivered by a Resource; benefits are usually related to alleviating pains (e.g., eliminate	String (max 1000)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	<p>Lifewatch ERIC is a European Research Infrastructure that provides e-Science research facilities to scientists, with a thematic focus on biodiversity, ecosystem functions and services research, including agroecology. Lifewatch ERIC achieves this by providing access to a multitude of resources and services that enable researchers to conduct their work and drive innovation.</p> <p>One of these services is the design and implementation of a Virtual Research Environment (VRE). A VRE is a web-based workspace that provides data users with a comprehensive suite of services and tools to support their data-related work. These tools include centralised access to data, data processing, visualisation of data, sharing of results, and other e-services. By using a VRE, data-users can work more efficiently with data, collaborate more effectively with other data-users stakeholders, and generate new knowledge in their field.</p> <p>In agroecology, a VRE provides data users with a platform for networking, data gathering and integration, data analysis and visualisation and artificial intelligence (AI) deep learning. The VRE allows data-users to identify and engage with their community while gathering and integrating data from various sources. The VRE offers computing power through high data</p>

	<p>undesired outcomes, obstacles or risks) or producing gains (e.g. increased performance, social gains, positive emotions or cost saving), c) list of customers, communities, users, etc. using the Resource.</p>						<p>analysis capacities such as the Picasso supercomputing centre, as well as storage capacity and data maintenance. Data users can also replicate and share the processes of data analysis, including workflows, models, and algorithms. Additionally, the VRE supports the use of Artificial intelligence (AI), deep learning and digital twins for more advanced research. The VRE in agroecology could also offer training and capacity building opportunities and facilitate dissemination and communication of research findings to relevant stakeholders.</p> <p>Using a VRE provides many benefits to the agroecology community. These benefits include improved efficiency and collaboration, access to advanced computing resources, the ability to analyse and visualise data in new and innovative ways, and the potential for increased research productivity and impact.</p>
<p>Tagline</p>	<p>Short catch-phrase for marketing and advertising purposes. It will be usually displayed close to the Resource name and should refer to the main value or purpose of the Resource.</p>	<p>String (max 100)</p>	<p>One</p>	<p>Mandatory</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Yes</p>	<p>Unleashing the data-users potential with Lifewatch ERIC's Virtual Research Environments - the ultimate tool for seamless collaboration and data-driven innovation in Agroecology</p>

Logo	Link to the logo/visual identity of the Resource. The logo will be visible at the Portal. If there is no specific logo for the Resource the logo of the Provider may be used.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	
Multimedia	Link to video, screenshots or slides showing details of the Resource.	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://www.lifewatch.eu/photo-video-gallery/
Multimedia Name	Short description of the Multimedia content	String (Max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Website Videos and photos
Use Cases	Link to use cases supported by this Resource.	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://community.lifewatch.eu/working-groups/biodt/
Use Cases Name	Short description of the Use Case content	String (Max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	BIODT : Biodiversity Digital Twin

5.3 Classification Information

	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Scientific Domain	The branch of science, a scientific discipline that is related to the Service/ Resource.	List of controlled values (See Table 9)	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agricultural Sciences <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Natural Sciences <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social Sciences
Scientific Sub-domain	The sub branch of science, the scientific subdiscipline that is related to the Service/Resource.	List of controlled values (See Table 9)	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agricultural Biotechnology <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Agriculture, Forestry & Fisheries <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biological Sciences <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Computer & Information Sciences <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Earth & Related Environmental Sciences <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Economics & Business <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environmental Biotechnology <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Environmental Engineering <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Political Sciences <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Social & Economic Geography <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Veterinary Sciences
Category	A named group of Resources that offer access to the same type of Service/Resource or capabilities.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Aggregators & Integrators <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Applications <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compute <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Consultancy & Support <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Data <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Data Analysis <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Data Management <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Data Storage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Development Resources <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Education & Training <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Instrument & Equipment <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Network <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Operations & Infrastructure Management Services <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Software
Sub-category	A named group of Service/Resources that offer access to the same type of Service/Resource or capabilities, within the defined Resource category	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Orchestration
Target Users	Type of users/customers that commissions a Provider to deliver a Service/Resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research Infrastructure Managers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research Managers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research Networks <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research Organisations <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Research Projects <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Researchers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Resource Managers <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Subjects
Access Type	The way a user can access the Service/Resource (Remote, Physical, Virtual, etc.)	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Virtual

		(See Table 10)					
Access Mode	Eligibility/criteria for granting access to users (excellence-based, free-conditionally, free etc.)	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	
Tags	Keywords associated to the Service/Resource to simplify search by relevant keywords.	String (max 50)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Blockchain, Data analysis, Data gathering, Data visualisation, Modelling, Simulation tools, Tokenization, Virtual Research Environment

5.4 Geographical and Language Availability Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Geographical Availability	Locations where the Service/Resource is offered.	List of controlled values (See Table 3)	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	
Language Availability	Languages of the (user interface of the) Service/Resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland

5.5 Resource Location Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
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Resource Geographic Location	List of geographic locations where data, samples, etc. are stored and processed	List of controlled values (See Table 3)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Spain
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5.6 Contact Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Main Contact/Resource Owner -First Name	First Name of the Service/Resource's main contact person/manager.	String (max 20)	One	Mandatory	No	No	José Manuel
Main Contact/Resource Owner -Last Name	Last Name of the Service/Resource's main contact person/manager.	String (max 20)	One	Mandatory	No	No	Ávila Castuera
Main Contact/Resource Owner -Email	Email of the Service/Resource's main contact person/manager.	Email	One	Mandatory	No	No	josem.avila@lifewatch.eu
Main Contact/Resource Owner -Phone	Telephone of the Service/Resource's main contact person/manager.	String (max 20)	One	Mandatory	No	No	0034609788444
Main Contact/Resource Owner -Position	Position of the Service/Resource's main contact person/manager.	String (max 20)	One	Optional	No	No	Agroecology Coordinator
Main Contact/Resource	The organisation to which the contact is affiliated	String (max	One	Optional	No	No	LifeWatch ERIC

Owner - Organisation		50)					
Public Contact - First Name	First Name of the Resource's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Iria
Public Contact - Last Name	Last Name of the Resource's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Soto - Embodas
Public Contact - Email	Email of the Resource's contact person or a generic email of the Provider to be displayed at the portal.	Email	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	iria.soto@lifewatch.eu
Public Contact – Phone	Telephone of the Resource's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	0034616812551
Public Contact – Position	Position of the Resource's contact person to be displayed at the portal.	String (max 20)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Agroecology Project Manager
Public Contact – Organisation	The organisation to which the contact is affiliated	String (max 50)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	LifeWatch ERIC
Other Contact – Helpdesk email	The email to ask more information from the Provider about this Resource.	Email	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	iria.soto@lifewatch.eu
Other Contact – Security Contact Email	The email to contact the Provider for critical security issues about this Resource.	Email	One	Mandatory	No	Yes	securas@lifewatch.eu

5.7 Maturity Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Technology Readiness Level	The Technology Readiness Level of the Resource (to be further updated in the context of the EOSC).	List of controlled values	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	7 - system prototype demonstration in operational environment
Life Cycle Status	Phase of the Resource life-cycle.	List of controlled values	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Beta
Certifications	List of certifications obtained for the Resource (including the certification body).	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	No
Standards	List of standards supported by the Resource.	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Darwin Core, Ecological Metadata Language, INSPIRE, Others
Open Source Technologies	List of open-source technologies supported by the Resource.	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Blockchain, DRAMA, GIS, Keycloak, Kubernetes, Minio, NodeJS, Openstack
Version	Version of the Resource that is in force.	String (max 10)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	
Last Update	Date of the latest update of the Resource.	Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	11/05/2023
Change Log	Summary of the Resource features updated from the previous version.	String (max 1000)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	https://tesseract.lifewatch.dev/

5.8 Dependencies Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
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Required Resources	List of other Resources required to use this Resource.	Resource IDs	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	No
Related Resources	List of other Resources that are commonly used with this Resource.	Resource IDs	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://metadatalogue.lifewatch.eu
Related Installations	List of suites or thematic installation in which the Resource is engaged or Providers (Provider groups) contributing to this Resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	Copernicus Climate Change Service
Catalogue	The Catalogue this Resource is originally registered at.	Catalogue ID	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	No

5.9 Attribution Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Funding Body	Name of the funding body that supported the development and/or operation of the Resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	European Commission (EC)
Funding Program	Name of the funding program that supported the development and/or operation of the Resource.	List of controlled values	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	Other
Grant/Project Name	Name of the project that supported the development and/or operation of the Resource.	String (max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	No	101058020 — AgroServ — HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01

5.10 Management Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Helpdesk Page	The URL to a webpage to ask for more information from the Provider about this Resource.	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://www.lifewatch.eu/help-desk/
User information	Link to the Resource user manual and documentation.	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://training.lifewatch.eu/
Terms of Use	Webpage describing the rules, Resource conditions and usage policy which one must agree to abide by to use the Resource.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://workdrive.lifewatch.eu/external/1e06f91acf1d951698c67502238dafc28de83caf61f2f4db6a52ca7b5849ed0
Privacy Policy	Link to the privacy policy applicable to the Resource.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	https://workdrive.lifewatch.eu/external/1e06f91acf1d951698c67502238dafc28de83caf61f2f4db6a52ca7b5849ed0
Access Policy	Information about the access policies that apply	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://workdrive.lifewatch.eu/external/1e06f91acf1d951698c67502238dafc28de83caf61f2f4db6a52ca7b5849ed0

Resource Level	Web Page with information about the levels of performance that a Provider is expected to deliver.	URL	One	Optional	Yes		No
Training Information	Webpage to training information on the Resource.	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://training.lifewatch.eu/
Status Monitoring	Webpage with monitoring information about this Resource	URL	One	Optional	Yes		https://status.lifewatch.dev
Maintenance	Webpage with information about planned maintenance windows for this Resource	URL	One	Optional	Yes		https://status.lifewatch.dev

5.11 Access and Order Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
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Order Type	Information on the order type (requires an ordering procedure, or no ordering and if fully open or requires authentication)	List of controlled values	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Order required
Order	Webpage through which an order for the Resource can be placed	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	securas@lifewatch.eu

5.12 Financial Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Payment Model	Webpage with the supported payment models and restrictions that apply to each of them	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	-
Pricing	Webpage with the information on the price scheme for this Resource in case the customer is charged for it.	URL	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	-

6 Additional Services/Resources information

Figure 18 Building blocks of the Service/Resource Description Template for AgroServ RI with Additional information

6.1 Marketing Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Main image for the descriptive sheet	This image will appear at the top of the description sheet and will be representative of the service.	URL	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	
General description	What the service does. Short description.	String (Max 1000)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	<p>A Virtual Research Environment (VRE) is a versatile web-based workspace that allows data users to conduct data-related work more efficiently and fosters collaboration among diverse users, with the goal of generating new knowledge. A VRE typically encompasses centralised data access, processing, visualisation, result sharing, and other e-services. The VRE can be utilised to address both scientific and managerial inquiries and has applications across various fields, including agroecology.</p>

							<p>In agroecology, the VRE is a web-based workspace that provides data-users with a platform for networking, data gathering and integration, data analysis and visualisation, and artificial intelligence (AI) deep learning. The VRE allows researchers to identify and engage with their community while gathering and integrating data from various sources. It offers computing power through high data analysis capacities such as the Picasso supercomputing centre, storage capacity, and data maintenance. Additionally, researchers can share their data analysis processes, including workflows, models, and algorithms. The VRE also supports the use of AI-deep learning and digital twins for more advanced research.</p> <p>Moreover, the VRE in agroecology could offer training and capacity building opportunities and facilitate the dissemination and communication of research findings to relevant stakeholders. By providing a collaborative workspace and access to essential services, the VRE in agroecology enables data-users to conduct data-related work more efficiently and effectively, leading to the generation of new knowledge and advancements in the field of agroecology.</p>
Functionalities it	Details of the regular and optional	String	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	A Virtual Research Environment (VRE) is

provides	features provided by the service	(Max 1000)					<p>a versatile web-based workspace that allows data users to conduct data-related work more efficiently and fosters collaboration among diverse users, with the goal of generating new knowledge. A VRE typically encompasses centralized data access, processing, visualization, result sharing, and other e-services. The VRE can be utilized to address both scientific and managerial inquiries and has applications across various fields, including agroecology.</p>
Users benefits	Eliminate undesired outcomes, obstacles or risks	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	<p>In agroecology, the VRE is a web-based workspace that provides data-users with a platform for networking, data gathering and integration, data analysis and visualization, and artificial intelligence (AI) deep learning. The VRE allows researchers to identify and engage with their community while gathering and integrating data from various sources. It offers computing power through high data analysis capacities such as the Picasso supercomputing center, storage capacity, and data maintenance. Additionally, researchers can share their data analysis processes, including workflows, models, and algorithms. The VRE also supports the use of AI-deep learning and digital twins for more advanced research.</p>
Users producing gains	Increase performance, social gains, positive emotions or cost saving	String (Max 100)	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	<p>Moreover, the VRE in agroecology could offer training and capacity building opportunities and facilitates the dissemination and communication of research findings to relevant stakeholders.</p>

							By providing a collaborative workspace and access to essential services, the VRE in agroecology enables data-users to conduct data-related work more efficiently and effectively, leading to the generation of new knowledge and advancements in the field of agroecology.
References	Customers, Communities, Publications	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	https://community.lifewatch.eu/
Use cases	Short description of the Use Case content	URL	Multiple	Optional	Yes	Yes	-

6.2 Location and country

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
Latitude	Latitude coordinate of the installation (in decimals: 60.924530 for 60°55'8.3"N)	String (7)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	virtual access
Longitude	Longitude coordinate of the installation (in decimals: 11.451259 for 1127°04.5"E)	String (7)	One	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	virtual access
Country Code	Country name abbreviation (France: FR)	Controlled values	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	virtual access

6.3 Dependencies Information

Field Name	Definition	Type	Multiplicity	Required	Public	Descriptive sheet	Example
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Required /Related Resource	Is the resource is required to use the service or only a related resource ?	List of controlled values	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Required
Required or Related Resource	Resource name	String (Max 100)	One				N2 gaz for Picarro Oven
Measured parameter	Measured parameters by the required/Related Resource	String (Max 100)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	-
Precision / Sensitivity	Measuring range and precision	String (Max 100)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	-
Analytical Capacity	Resource measurement capacity (sampling frequency for continuous measurements, samples processed per day or per hour, ...)	String (Max 100)	One	Optional	Yes	Yes	Sampling frequency : 5 mins

7 Conclusion and next steps

AgroServ aims to develop an open, trusted and user-friendly portal to a harmonised and aggregated Catalogues of 12 Research Infrastructure Services and Resources, interoperable with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) catalogue and accessible by different users and RIs access managers. The deliverable addresses the suggested typology of RI installations and services, the installations and services catalogues contents and its main functionalities.

The main functionalities for the Agroserv Portal that will be implemented in 3 subsequent phases are: 1) Collect the data in structured description models, 2) Publish the data in catalogues accessible to all users 3) Make data interoperable with other scientific fields and their catalogues.

The possibility to implement a further functionality for including in the portal the Agroserv Living Labs (WP6) adding a specific functionality to register the LL participants will be also evaluated.

The objectives of setting up a tool for collecting information on service providers and services and a catalogue to facilitate their discovery have been achieved. The collection tool is currently being deployed in all the research infrastructures or installations that wish to participate in the population of European catalogues with their metadata. Training sessions (of approximately 2 hours) are scheduled to guide managers to the data entry forms. The use of the tool remains very simple and does not require particular computer skills.

The catalogues of installations and their services are already online and can be reached using the following links

<https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/platform/list/agroserv>

<https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/service/list/agroserv>

The installations are presented in the form of cards on which you can find the description of the installation and a link to a catalogue of services and resources that the installation is proposing to users. We have already identified limitations in some search filters and they will be improved in the coming months, as well as the descriptive sheets and the homepage of the catalogues. This change will be done next September and will aim to develop a visually more attractive version as well as a more advanced filter system, allowing to launch searches on all the stored information on the installations. It is important to highlight that the catalogue model is by essence an evolutive object and the constant inclusion of feedback from providers and users will allow us to design the most adapted version to the needs of the communities.

The standard description models have been extensively discussed within working groups in order to enrich them with specific information to the fields of agroecology. It is possible that these

extensions of the controlled values of the EOSC standard model will be added permanently to the model proposed by EOSC so that all agroecology installations that want to be interoperable with EOSC can use the same controlled vocabulary.

The next step will be dedicated to the implementation of the interoperability tools. We have already identified 2 development axes that aim to increase synergies between the different scientific domains:

- Axis 1: Develop scientific and technical interoperability for multidisciplinary and multi-RIs services provision. To ensure good scientific interoperability, we must verify that all the vocabulary used to describe installations, services, resources and experiments is common to several scientific fields.
- Axis 2: Develop tools to disseminate our information in various multidisciplinary catalogues, increase our visibility and encourage innovative multidisciplinary, interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary projects.

We will support service providers during the data entry phase of their RIs and services by offering them terms from thesauri of different scientific domains. They will then be able to choose the most appropriate term to ensure an interdisciplinary understanding. The joint use of these vocabularies from different domains may lead to harmonisation or correspondence between the terms used. In addition, the use of terms identified in the thesauri will make it possible to associate machine-readable URIs and thus increase the visibility of the services to which they are associated. The conjunction of the harmonisation/enrichment of the standard description models and the use of APIs between catalogues will also allow to disseminate largely to all scientific domains the capabilities developed in AgroServ. These models can be associated with descriptions using ontologies to generate RDF graphs, which are also machine-readable.

All the points developed above, which are the facilitation of information collection, enrichment of the description models, use of controlled vocabularies, generation of RDF format and automatic dissemination in a wide range of catalogues will increase the visibility of the service offers, make their use more efficient and prepare the ground for research and innovation projects.

8 Appendix 1

8.1 Providers Scientific Domain/Category Classification

Table 1 Providers Scientific Domain/Category Classification

No .	Scientific Domain	No .	Category	Description
1	Biological & Medical Sciences	1	Agronomy, Forestry and Plant Breeding Centres	Facilities that enable open field and forest experiments to test the impact of management practices and environmental conditions on soil, crop, and primary production. These include plants and trees ex-situ collections, experimental facilities for controlled crosses and propagation, and population genetics field testing. The facilities are relevant for Biological- and Environmental Sciences.
		2	Animal Facilities	Facilities that provide the husbandry of animals and services to the biomedical research community are usually equipped with highly automated systems that provide the best possible conditions for animal reproduction and maintenance. The main activity is the reproduction and maintenance of animal stocks either of inbred strains or genetically engineered animals, such as transgenic and knockout mouse lines, or even chemically-induced mutants.
		3	Collections of Biological Resources (e.g. Microorganisms, Biobanks and Seed Banks)	Facilities for storage of collections of microorganisms, biological material and the associated data and information facilities for a population or a large subset of a population, maintained under controlled conditions (temperature, humidity, atmosphere, etc.). The biological resources, including microorganisms, human/animal cells, tissue, blood and DNA, seeds of crops, trees and wild plant species, are conserved for their genetic endowment. Databases established on these provide holistic information on each accession with scientific descriptors, ethnobotanical/zoological/microbiological/medical knowledge, including to establish intellectual property rights and ownership over the biomaterial stored
		4	Bioinformatics Facilities	Bioinformatics facilities generate knowledge through computer analysis of biological data. These can consist of the information stored in the genetic code, but also experimental results from various sources, patient statistics, and scientific literature. Research in bioinformatics includes method development for storage, retrieval, and analysis of the data. Bioinformatics is a rapidly developing branch of biology and is highly interdisciplinary, using techniques and concepts from informatics, statistics, mathematics, chemistry, biochemistry, physics, and linguistics. It has many practical applications in

		different areas of biology and medicine.
5	Biological/Biomedical Engineering and Biotechnology/Nanotechnology Research Facilities	Facilities that are dedicated to application of concepts and methods of bioscience and/or nanoscience, and/or use of living systems and organisms to develop solutions to problems in life- and preclinical sciences using engineering methodologies.
6	Biomedical Imaging Facilities	Facilities are equipped for the visualisation, characterisation and measurement of biological processes at the cellular and tissue levels in humans and other living systems.
7	Cell Culture Facilities	Facilities that are equipped to provide robust support for isolation and culture of a variety of cell lines (like mammalian and insect cell lines, mouse and human embryonic stem cells), including serum preparation, feeders, growth factors and mycoplasma testing, maybe on serum-based or serum-free media.
8	Environmental Health Research Facilities	Environmental health research addresses all potential hazards caused to a human being or an animal by external physical, chemical, and biological factors, and all the related factors impacting behaviours. It encompasses the assessment and control of those environmental factors that can potentially affect health. It is targeted toward preventing disease and creating health-supportive environments. This definition excludes behaviour not related to the environment, as well as behaviour related to the social and cultural environment, and genetics. This category includes toxicology and infectious diseases facilities as well as epidemiological study centres.
9	Genomic, Transcriptomic, Proteomics and Metabolomics Facilities	Multiple sites ranging from single laboratory DNA sequencing and RNA transcript analysis facilities run by biologists for their own department's research to high-throughput facilities aimed at providing a sophisticated service for a broad community of biologists run by informaticians, biologists and engineers. Proteomics: physical chemistry developments for clinical and biological applications getting access to protein networks linked to the physiological and pathological states of the cells. This includes nutrigenomics research.
10	Structural Biology Facilities	Facilities, which are equipped for visualisation, characterisation, and measurement of biological processes at the molecular level in humans and other living systems. Main technologies include protein crystallisation, X-ray diffraction, mass spectrometry, DSC.

		11	Systems Biology/Computational Biology Facilities	Laboratories that combine all relevant scientific disciplines and the know-how to integrate experimental data with computational and theoretical approaches with the aim of targeting, understanding and engineering pathways, cells, organs and complete organisms.
		12	Other	
2	Chemistry & Material Sciences	1	Analytical Facilities	All facilities where analytical tools are used are based on one of the following probes or methods: electrons, photons, neutrons, radio frequency, NMR, or analytical chemistry. It does include Surface Science Laboratories dedicated to analysis and characterization of surface and interface phenomena. Different users would come from the scientific domains Chemistry, Earth science, Bio-Medical (including forensic) science and different sensitivities (Analytical Chemistry, electron microscopy laboratories); NMR facilities; surface science laboratories; x-ray diffraction; Electron Microscopy Laboratories, aspects in life sciences, earth, forensics; Surface Science Laboratories.
		2	Chemical Libraries and Screening Facilities	Digital libraries related to chemistry as well as screening facilities.
		3	Intense Light Sources	All facilities that provide access to intense light radiation sources as used for lasers, synchrotrons, Free Electron Lasers. The facilities are relevant to the scientific domains of Physics, Chemistry, Bio-Medical Sciences, Earth and Environmental Sciences, Humanities & Arts, Information Science & Technology; Laser Sources for materials synthesis laboratories; Laser Sources for spectroscopy laboratories; Synchrotron Light Sources and X-Ray Diffraction Facilities.
		4	Intense Neutron Sources	Accelerator-based neutron source facility that provides the intense pulsed neutron beam.
		5	Materials Synthesis or Testing Facilities	All single or multi-sited facilities are run by engineers and materials scientists to process or test materials concerning predefined specifications. It includes testing and processing equipment, structural and properties characterization instruments. The facilities are relevant to the scientific domains of Engineering, Materials Sciences, Physics, and Chemistry.
		6	Pilot Plants for Process Testing	Plants where processes in biological or chemical systems, including bioenergy/biorefinery research and food processing research, are tested on a pilot level scale. Biology, Chemistry.
		7	Reference Material Repositories	Facilities providing materials with at least one standardised and fully described property that can be used in measurements e.g. as a standard for calibration of instruments or as a reference for measuring other materials.

3	Earth & Environmental Sciences	8	Other	
		1	Acoustic Monitoring Stations	Non-audible very low-frequency waves infrasound stations, (volcano meteors monitoring, avalanches, landslides); audible frequency stations and hydroacoustic stations (marine mammals, multi-beam, acoustic tomography, echosounders, sodar); high-frequency stations (T- phase stations).
		2	Atmospheric Measurement Facilities	Meteorological stations (all physical parameters that can be observed) ; Global Atmospheric Watch (GAW); Airglow; Ionospheric stations (all sky cameras, ionospheric radar); brewers; lidars; chemical compositions, pollution and radionuclides facilities; This includes atmospheric test chambers, used to conduct controlled experiments for climate change research and atmosphere related problems.
		3	Earth Observation Satellites	Including Optical-IR Earth Observation satellites and Radar Earth Observation satellites. Satellite imaging.
		4	Earth, Ocean, Marine, Freshwater, and Atmosphere Data Centres	Installations for the exchange of earth, oceanographic, marine, freshwater and atmospheric data and information, and advisory services in the field of the earth, ocean, marine, freshwater and atmospheric data management. National Data Centres, Designated National Agencies for international data exchange and Satellite Data Centres represent the backbone of the data and information infrastructure. National networks are usually put in place to interconnect the data centres of major national institutes. The overall objective is to significantly improve the overview and access to data and data analysis from government and research institutes.
		5	Environmental Management Infrastructures	Pilot facilities and experimental infrastructures for management, ecological restoration and environmental mitigation of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems in natural or degraded conditions (including hydrological and soil management field facilities; decontamination and bioremediation facilities and pilot plants).
		6	In Situ Earth Observatories	Installations and sensor technologies deployed in situ to collect environmental data (including physical, chemical and biological observations) in support of terrestrial environmental research and management activities. These facilities, including ecological habitat field stations, provide a base for trans-disciplinary research and training, with access to terrestrial field sites for the survey and experimental opportunities and often supporting environmental observations and the collection of long-term time series data sets (i.e. on biodiversity).

		7	In Situ Marine/Freshwater Observatories	Installations and sensor technologies deployed in situ to collect environmental data (including physical, chemical and biological observations) in support of aquatic environmental research and management activities. These facilities, including marine/freshwater research centres, provide a base for transdisciplinary research and training, with access to marine and freshwater field sites, and equipment (including research vessels that may carry large exchangeable underwater equipment/instruments) for the survey and experimental opportunities and often supporting environmental observations and the collection of long-term time series data sets (i.e. on biodiversity). Typical equipment includes Buoys; Argo; gliders; autonomous underwater vehicles; remotely operated vehicles (Victor); Tide gauges; deep-sea laboratories. Ship time for stock assessments, polar supply, naval research and educational courses and non-academic research are not considered in this context. For this inventory, the atmospheric measurement facilities are kept as a separate category. This implies that some marine research centres will also fall under this category if they host an atmospheric measurement site.
		8	Natural History Collections	Facilities that serve as a library of organisms that have lived and/or are living on Earth and curation sites for materials relevant for planetary exploration. They contribute to specific research and public education in an easily accessible venue.
		9	Other	
4	Information Science & Technology	1	Centralised Computing Facilities	Single-sited facilities with a centralised control that enable high-performance computing through supercomputers. These are relevant to all scientific domains.
		2	Communication Networks	Facilities responsible, at national or international levels, for the provision of data communications networks, capacity and services to the research and education community in all scientific domains. The networks typically connect other networks at international, regional or metropolitan level.
		3	Complex Data Facilities	Facilities to store huge and high dimensional data volumes and apply statistical methods to classify or cluster the data to extract valuable information. The facilities are relevant to Bio-Medical Sciences; Earth and Environmental Sciences; Physics; Astrophysics; Social Sciences.

		4	Distributed Computing Facilities	Facilities for virtualisation, grid and cloud computing, or capability computing that are loosely coupled, heterogeneous, and geographically dispersed distributed system with non-interactive workloads that involve a large number of files. They federate, share and coordinate distributed resources from different organisations that are not subject to centralised control, using open, general-purpose and in some cases standard protocols and interfaces to deliver non-trivial qualities of service relevant to all scientific domains.
		5	Software Service Facilities	Facilities that provide access to well fabricated software for modelling, simulation, development, control and optimization, including software libraries/repositories or support services for the implementation of the software, their maintenance and adaptation to new hardware platforms as well consultation regarding the proper use of the software as well as training facilities for users. These are relevant to all scientific domains.
		6	Other	
5	Social Sciences	1	Data Archives, Data Repositories and Collections	A digital data archive is a centre of expertise in data acquisition, preservation, management, dissemination and promotion of access to the national and international collections and repositories of digital data. These types of RIs are particularly acute to the social sciences, which often rely on the aggregation of longitudinal data, and to the humanities, which often rely on preservation, but they can be relevant for other domains, particularly, the life and environmental sciences and the medical sciences.
		2	Data mining and Analysis (Methodological) Centres, including statistical analysis	Centres of expertise or methodological resources for extracting patterns from large data sets by combining methods from statistics and artificial intelligence. These RIs enable researchers to overcome the challenge of working with increasingly larger data sets. Data mining and statistical techniques populate every scientific domain but what counts as data is domain specific. Therefore, this category should be understood as specific to social sciences because it refers to data in the social sciences.
		3	National Statistical Facilities (offices)	Centres of expertise responsible for the collection and publication of statistics related to the economy, population and society at international, national and regional levels. These infrastructures have been traditionally created by the states but constitute as well powerful resources for social scientists in particular.

		4	Registers and Surveyed Studies/Databases	Organized and systematic collection of data (time or spatial series) for one or more purposes (research, evidence-based policy, non-governmental organisations) in digital form or not. These types of RIs are particularly acute to the social sciences, which often rely on the aggregation of masses of longitudinal data but they can be relevant for all the other domains, that is, the humanities, the life and environmental sciences, the physical sciences and engineering, and the medical sciences.
		5	Research Data Service Facilities	Facilities for clustering research data and making it permanently accessible, as well as facilities for the provision of all sorts of data services. These often include meta- infrastructures. These types of RIs are particularly relevant to Humanities and Arts; Social Sciences, Medical sciences.
		6	Other	
6	Other	1	Other	

Source : MERIL

8.2 Providers Type Classification

Table 2 Classification of Providers based on their Type

No.	Provider Type	Description
1	Single-sited	The Provider has one main physical location for users.
2	Distributed	The Provider has multiple physical locations but a unified management structure and a single coordination center.
3	Mobile	The Provider is changing its physical location on a regular basis (e.g., satellites, research vessels)
4	Virtual	The Provider is exclusively an electronic resource/service.
5	Other	

8.3 Providers and Services/Resources Location Classification

Table 3 Providers and Services/Resources Location

No.	Country Abbreviation	Country name
1	FR	France
2	IT	Italy
3	BE	Belgium
4	DK	Denmark
5	CZ	Czech Republic
6	PT	Portugal
7	UK	United Kingdom
8	DE	Germany
9	FI	Finland
10	ES	Spain
11	NL	Netherlands
12	RO	Romania
13	AT	Austria

14	BG	Bulgaria
15	IE	Ireland
16	IL	Israel
17	LT	Lithuania
18	NO	Norway
19	SE	Sweden
20	SI	Slovenia
21	CH	Switzerland
22	GR	Greece
23	PL	Poland
24	RS	Serbia

8.4 Providers ESFRI Domain Classification

Table 4 Classification of Providers based on their ESFRI Domain

No.	ESFRI Domain
1	Energy
2	Environment
3	Health & Food
4	Physical Sciences & Engineering
5	Social & Cultural Innovation
6	Data, Computing and Digital Research Infrastructures
7	Other

8.5 Providers ESFRI type Classification

Table 5 Classification of Providers based on their ESFRI Types

No.	Provider ESFRI Status
1	RI is a node of an ESFRI project
2	RI is an ESFRI project
3	RI is an ESFRI landmark
4	Not an ESFRI project or landmark
5	Other

8.6 Providers Areas of Activity Classification

Table 6 Classification of Providers based on their Areas of Activity

No.	Provider Areas of Activity
1	Basic research
2	Applied research
3	Technological development

8.7 Providers Societal Grand Challenges Classification

Table 7 Providers Societal Grand Challenges Classification

N	Provider Societal Grand Challenges
1	Health, demographic change and wellbeing
2	Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research and the Bioeconomy
3	Secure, clean and efficient energy
4	Smart, green and integrated transport
5	Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials
6	Europe in a changing world – inclusive, innovative, and reflective societies
7	Secure societies – protecting the freedom and security of Europe and its citizens

8.8 Providers Sustainable Development Goals Classification

Table 8 Providers Sustainable Development Goals Classification

No.	Sustainable Development Goals
1	No poverty
2	Zero hunger
3	Good health and well-being
4	Quality education
5	Gender equality
6	Clean water and sanitation
7	Affordable and clean energy
8	Decent work and economic growth
9	Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure
10	Reduced inequality
11	Sustainable cities and communities
12	Responsible consumption and production
13	Climate action
14	Life below water
15	Life on land
16	Peace, justice and strong institutions
17	Partnership for the goals

8.9 Services/Resources Scientific Domain Classification

Table 9 Services/Resources Scientific Domain Classification

No	Scientific Domain	Description	No	Scientific Subdomain
1	Natural Sciences	Any of the sciences (such as physics, chemistry, or biology) that deal with matter, energy, and their interrelations and transformations or with objectively measurable phenomena (Merriam-Webster).	1	Computer sciences
			2	Information sciences
			3	Earth sciences
			4	Biological sciences
			5	Physical sciences
			6	Chemical sciences
			7	Biological and biomedical imagine
2	Engineering & Technology	The application of science and mathematics by which the properties of matter and the sources of energy in nature are made useful to people (Merriam- Webster).	1	Civil engineering
			2	Electrical, electronic and information engineering
			3	Mechanical engineering
			4	Aerospace engineering
			5	Chemical engineering
			6	Materials engineering
			7	Bioengineering and Biomedical engineering
			8	Environmental engineering
			9	Environmental biotechnology
			10	Industrial biotechnology
			11	Micro and Nanotechnology
3	Agricultural Sciences	Sciences dealing with food and fibre production and processing. They include the technologies of soil cultivation, crop cultivation and harvesting, animal production, and the processing of plant and animal products for human consumption and use (Britannica).	1	Agribusiness
			2	Agricultural Biotechnology
			3	Agricultural Chemistry
			4	Agricultural Economics & Social Science
			5	Agricultural Education
			6	Agricultural Geography
			7	Agricultural Marketing
			8	Agricultural Microbiology
			9	Agricultural Technology, Machinery & Mechanization
			10	Agroecology
			11	Agronomy (Includes Botany, Plant Physiology, Theoretical Production Ecology, Horticulture, Plant Breeding, Plant Fertilisation)
			12	Agrophysics
			13	Animal Science (Includes Animal/Poultry Breeding, Animal Husbandry, Animal Nutrition, Livestock Systems)

			14	Aquaculture, Fisheries & Marine Science
			15	Entomology & Plant Pathology
			16	Environmental Science & Agro-ecosystem
			17	Farm Management
			18	Food Science & Post-Harvest Technology
			19	Irrigation & Water Management
			20	Organic agriculture
			21	Range-Land Management
			22	Rural Buildings & Agro-Forest Land Planning
			23	Soil Science (Includes Biodiversity)
			24	Veterinary Sciences
			25	Waste Management
			26	Weed Science
			27	Food System
			28	Biological and biomedical imagine
4	Social Sciences	A branch of science that deals with the institutions and functioning of human society and with the interpersonal relationships of individuals as members of society (Merriam-Webster).	1	Psychology behavioural science
			2	Economics, finance and business
			3	Educational sciences
			4	Sociology
			5	Political sciences
			6	Social and economic geography
			7	Media and communications
5	Interdisciplinary	Involving two or more scientific disciplines/domains with methodologies and theories from all of them (Merriam-Webster).	1	Interdisciplinary
6	Multidisciplinary	Involving multiple disciplines/domains for research goals set under one thematic umbrella (Morton et al., 2015).	1	Multidisciplinary
7	Transdisciplinary	Integrating different scientific disciplines/domains and involving non-academic stakeholders in the research process (Morton et al., 2015).	1	Transdisciplinary

Source: MERIL;

https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/Scientific_Disciplines

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Agricultural_science

https://www.cun.it/uploads/storico/settori_scientifico_disciplinari_english.pdf

<https://www.britannica.com/science/agricultural-sciences/Major-divisions>

https://www.whed.net/search_by_fos.php?fos=Agriculture

<https://www.fao.org/agrovoc/releases>

Morton et al. (2015) <http://www.jstor.org/stable/26270306>

8.10 Services/Resources Access Type Classification

Table 10 Classification of services and resources based on their Access Type

No.	Access Type	Description
1	Remote	Services and Resources are delivered remotely with the use of a physical infrastructure. The user is able to remotely work with the physical RI without the need of physical presence.
2	Physical	Services and resources require a physical presence of the user. The user can only access the RI if he is physically present in the specific location that the RI is offered.
3	Virtual	The service/resource is delivered through a virtual infrastructure that the use may access virtually through the web or an intranet.
4	Mail-in	Samples are sent in to for e.g. analysis and the results are returned to the user without the user actually accessing the RI
5	Other	